

Aug4Sat: Synthetic Satellite Imagery Generation for Remote Sensing Applications

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Abstract

Generating synthetic satellite imagery for geographically underrepresented regions requires either paired segmentation maps, which creates a circular annotation dependency, or general-purpose diffusion models, which produce geographically incorrect scenes. Aug4Sat resolves this through VLM-guided captioning: a vision-language model automatically captions raw regional satellite chips to build LoRA training data, and a companion LLM reproduces the caption distribution at inference time, aligning training and inference semantics without manual annotation. Evaluated on East African imagery, Aug4Sat achieves 95–100% mean feature controllability for single-feature configurations and strong perceptual diversity (LPIPS: 0.59 across 1,002 images). Comparison against vanilla SDXL shows that standard aggregate spectral metrics systematically favour geographically incorrect outputs, motivating domain-aware evaluation for regional generative models. **Keywords:** synthetic satellite imagery, LoRA, VLM-guided captioning, regional domain adaptation, diffusion models, remote sensing

1. Introduction

Satellite imagery analysis has advanced rapidly through deep learning, enabling land cover mapping, disaster monitoring, and humanitarian planning at scale (Zhu et al. 2017). Yet progress is uneven. Models trained on well-resourced regions generalise poorly to developing countries, conflict zones, and areas where acquisition infrastructure is limited, because annotated satellite imagery from these regions is scarce and public benchmark datasets are strongly skewed toward affluent geographies (Ma et al. 2019; Shankar et al. 2017). One path forward is generating synthetic imagery that looks like the target region, not like the global average.

Two approaches exist, each with a fundamental limitation. Segmentation-conditioned pipelines offer spatial control through conditioning on layout maps, but require paired image-segmentation: exactly the labelled resource that is missing in data-scarce settings (Castro Lopes et al. 2025).

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General-purpose text-to-image diffusion models need no such labels, but produce geographically incorrect imagery for underrepresented regions regardless of how they are prompted, because their training distributions are dominated by imagery from other parts of the world (Khanna et al. 2024).

Aug4Sat is designed around the insight that a vision-language model can read raw regional satellite chips and write domain-specific captions for them, automatically and without human annotation. Those captions become LoRA training data. At inference time, a companion LLM generates prompts that match the vocabulary and style of those training captions, ensuring the model receives prompts that fall within its training distribution. The result is controllable, regionally accurate synthetic satellite imagery built from nothing but a small set of raw chips from the target region.

2. Methodology

2.1. VLM-Guided LoRA Training

Figure 1 shows the data preparation pipeline. High-resolution imagery at 0.5 m spatial resolution from Addis Ababa and Mogadishu is divided into 1024×1024 chips and filtered for cloud cover, blur, and low contrast. Retained chips are captioned by Qwen3-VL-8B-Instruct, generating 50–80 word descriptions with remote sensing vocabulary, removing the need for manual annotation. Manual inspection removes temporal anomalies. The 322 curated image-caption pairs fine-tune SDXL via LoRA (rank 16, alpha 32, 3,500 steps, lr 1×10^{-4} , cosine annealing), yielding ~ 300 MB adapter weights (Hu et al. 2022). SDXL operates in a compressed latent space, making 1024×1024 generation computationally tractable (Rombach et al. 2022). Caption quality is used deliberately as the primary lever for prompt-following fidelity, following evidence that detailed training captions are the main determinant of controllability in text-to-image models (Betker et al. 2023).

Figure 1: VLM-guided data preparation and LoRA training. Imagery is tiled, quality-filtered, automatically captioned by VLM, manually verified, and used to fine-tune SDXL via LoRA.

2.2. LLM-Guided Inference and Caption Alignment

Users specify scene features through a hierarchical system covering 14+ controls across water bodies, vegetation, infrastructure, and buildings. Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct translates these specifications

into captions that match the VLM training vocabulary. Both models share Qwen architectural lineage, so inference prompts fall naturally within the LoRA training caption distribution. This alignment is the mechanism behind controllability. Generic prompts (e.g., “rural scene with vegetation”) that break this alignment achieved only 25% feature recall; domain-aligned Qwen2.5 prompts increased recall to 100% for vegetation configurations, showing that caption distribution alignment, not just prompt phrasing, determines controllability.

2.3. Validation

Feature controllability is assessed via DeepLabV3+ with ResNet50 encoder (trained on 1,000 regional satellite chips, mIoU: 0.623), segmenting into six classes: background, water, bareland, vegetation, roads, buildings. Feature recall per configuration is the mean of per-feature recall values, each computed as an integer fraction of images in which the feature exceeds 2% coverage (e.g., 19/20 = 95%). Perceptual diversity is measured by pairwise LPIPS with AlexNet backbone (Zhang et al. 2018), where higher values indicate greater diversity. Domain quality is assessed through spectral histogram comparison and GLCM texture analysis against 500 real regional chips.

3. Results

3.1. Feature Controllability

Table 1 presents controllability results ($n = 20$ per single-feature configuration; $n = 50$ for mixed). Single-feature configurations achieve 95–100% mean recall. Urban scenes produce reliable building coverage ($37.2 \pm 10.8\%$) co-occurring with roads ($6.6 \pm 2.5\%$). Vegetation reaches 100% recall with 54.0% mean coverage via alignment. Water scenes show the high variance ($33.7 \pm 22.5\%$), reflecting compositional variability in coastal scenes. Mixed-feature recall drops to 71.0% (per-feature: grassland 82%, sparse trees 82%, residential 78%, roads 52%, coastal water 14%), consistent with competing spatial constraints under text-only conditioning. Bareland appears persistently across all configurations (36–96%), reflecting the semi-arid character of the training domain.

Experiment	Requested	Recall	Primary	Secondary
Urban Only	Buildings+Roads	97.5%	Buildings: $37.2 \pm 10.8\%$	Roads: $6.6 \pm 2.5\%$
Water Only	Coastal water	95.0%	Water: $33.7 \pm 22.5\%$	Bareld: $36.3 \pm 7.6\%$
Vegetation Only	Forest+Grassland	100.0%	Vegetation: $54.0 \pm 0.0\%$	Bareld: $45.3 \pm 0.0\%$
Div Mixed	Mixed features	71.0%	Bareld: $73.8 \pm 17.8\%$	Buildings: $13.3 \pm 11.1\%$

Table 1: Feature controllability (mean \pm std coverage). Recall is the mean across requested features; per-feature recall is always an integer fraction of images.

3.2. Diversity and Domain Quality

Figure 2 shows representative outputs across the three dominant configurations. Pairwise LPIPS across 1,002 baseline images yields mean 0.59 (± 0.07), confirming strong perceptual diversity. Per-configuration LPIPS ranges from 0.44 (urban) to 0.64 (vegetation). Table 2 presents domain-

Figure 2: Representative Aug4Sat outputs per dominant land-cover class, demonstrating intra-class visual diversity without segmentation map conditioning.

specific metrics against 500 real regional chips. Spectral histogram intersection of 0.747 indicates good colour overlap. GLCM texture similarity of 68.3% shows that LoRA outputs are systematically smoother than real chips (contrast -35.2% , dissimilarity -30.8%), consistent with known over-smoothing in diffusion model denoising (Tang et al. 2024), while spatial correlation is the best-matched texture feature ($+4.7\%$).

Metric	Value	Interpretation
Spectral histogram intersection	0.747	Good colour overlap
KL divergence	0.187	Low distribution shift
Earth mover’s distance	14.27	Moderate spectral distance
GLCM texture similarity	68.3%	Good; outputs over-smoothed
LPIPS diversity \uparrow	0.590	High inter-image diversity

Table 2: Domain-specific evaluation vs real regional chips ($n=500$ spectral, $n=100$ texture). LPIPS \uparrow : higher values indicate greater diversity.

Figure 3: Aug4Sat (top) vs vanilla SDXL (bottom), identical prompts and seeds. Aug4Sat reproduces the semi-arid East African regional style; vanilla SDXL produces temperate-region scenes despite scoring higher on aggregate spectral metrics.

3.3. Baseline Comparison: The Metric Adequacy Problem

Comparing Aug4Sat against vanilla SDXL using identical settings, vanilla SDXL scores higher on aggregate metrics (+0.065 histogram intersection, +22.4% texture similarity). *Figure 3* shows why this is misleading. Vanilla SDXL consistently produces temperate-region scenes: European and American road grids, green parks, Atlantic coastlines, unrepresentative of the semi-arid Horn of Africa. Its higher aggregate scores reflect its global pretraining distribution, not regional accuracy. Aug4Sat outputs reproduce the ochre semi-arid palette, informal settlement morphology, and land cover patterns of Mogadishu and Addis Ababa across all configurations. A base model can score well on aggregate metrics by accident of broad pretraining while producing regionally wrong imagery. Domain-aware evaluation, combining visual inspection with segmentation-based feature verification, is necessary for assessing geographically specialised generative models.

4. Discussion

Aug4Sat makes three connected contributions. VLM-guided captioning removes the annotation dependency that constrains segmentation-conditioned approaches, requiring only raw regional chips. Training-inference caption alignment through architecturally compatible Qwen models is the identifiable mechanism behind the controllability gains, not prompt engineering alone. The baseline comparison provides empirical evidence that aggregate spectral metrics can favour geographically incorrect outputs, a finding relevant to how regional generative models are evaluated more broadly. Limitations include semi-arid regional bias from two training cities, reduced mixed-scene controllability under text-only conditioning (coastal water at 14% in mixed configurations), and RGB-only generation that precludes quantitative multispectral analysis. The most direct next step is downstream scene classification validation using prompt-derived labels, to assess whether Aug4Sat improves generalisation of classifiers to underrepresented regions.

5. System and Reproducibility

Aug4Sat provides an interactive Gradio interface for feature-based scene specification, running on a single NVIDIA T4 (16 GB VRAM) at approximately 35 seconds per 1024×1024 image with fixed-seed reproducibility. All components are publicly released: training code, LoRA weights on Hugging Face, Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct prompting scripts, and the Gradio interface.

GitHub: <https://github.com/AmirRoblex/Aug4Sat> Model: <https://huggingface.co/Sam-Roblex/LoRA-Sat>

6. Conclusions

Aug4Sat shows that VLM-guided captioning of raw regional imagery, combined with LLM-aligned inference prompting and LoRA fine-tuning, produces controllable and regionally accurate synthetic satellite imagery without manual annotation. The framework achieves 95–100% mean feature recall for single-feature configurations and high perceptual diversity across 1,002 generated images. The finding that aggregate spectral metrics can prefer geographically incorrect outputs motivates domain-aware evaluation practice for regional generative models in remote sensing.

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